

Long-lasting biofouling formation on transparent fouling-release coatings for the construction of efficient closed photobioreactors

Y. Soriano-Jerez^a, L. García-Abad^a, M.C. Cerón-García^{a*}, J. J. Gallardo-Rodríguez^a, C. Bressy^b, F. García-Camacho^a, E. Molina-Grima^a

^a Department of Chemical Engineering and Research Centre CIAIMBITAL, University of Almería, 04120, Almería (Spain)

^b Laboratoire MAPIEM, U.R. 4323, SeaTech Ecole d'Ingénieur, Université de Toulon, CS 60584, 83041 Toulon Cedex 9, France

* Corresponding author: mcceron@ual.es

Address: Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Almería, Carretera Sacramento s/n. 04120, Almería (Spain)

Telephone number: +34 950015891

Fax: +34 950 015484

1 **Abstract**

2 In order to build an efficient closed-photobioreactor in which biofouling formation is
3 avoided, a non-toxic coating with high transparency that can be applied on to the
4 interior surface of the closed-photobioreactor (PBR) walls is required; this is so that
5 microalgae cells cannot adhere to them. Nowadays, amphiphilic copolymers are being
6 used to inhibit microorganism adhesion, so poly(dimethylsiloxane)-based coatings
7 mixed with poly(ethylene glycol)-based copolymers are a good alternative for obtaining
8 a transparent and non-toxic coating with antibiofouling properties. All of the 7 coatings
9 tested in this work offer a good alternative to glass because they present lower cell
10 adhesion. DBE-311 copolymer proved to be the best option due to its low cell adhesion
11 and high transmittance. Furthermore, the results can be explained through the XDLVO
12 theory since the tested coatings create a very high energy barrier that microalgae cells
13 cannot overcome.

14 **Keywords**

15 Biofouling, marine microalgae, XDLVO theory, transparent fouling-release coatings,
16 *Nannochloropsis gaditana*

17 **1. Introduction**

18 Microalgae are photosynthetic microorganisms that are used to obtain a wide range of
19 products for different applications; these include high-value products, which can be
20 used as dietary supplements (omega-3 or proteins), in cosmetics or even in biomedicine,
21 since they are able to produce anticancer and antimicrobial substances (Barkia, Saari,
22 and Manning 2019). On the other hand, microalgae can be used to obtain low-value
23 products such as biodiesel, biofertilizers, biostimulants or even be used in wastewater
24 treatment (Al-Jabri et al. 2021; Zerrouh et al. 2017a). Due to the increasing demand for
25 these products over the past few years, it is now more important than ever to have an

26 economical, effective and long-lasting culture system to meet this demand (Zerriouh et
27 al. 2017a). One of the main issues in this type of culture system is biofouling.
28 Biofouling occurs when microorganisms adhere to surfaces that are exposed to aqueous
29 environments (Lejars, Margailan, and Bressy 2012). It mainly takes place in two steps:
30 (i) the formation of a conditioning film, which occurs when organic molecules such as
31 proteins or polysaccharides are physically adsorbed on to the walls of the PBRs; and (ii)
32 the attachment of cells to the conditioning film (Zerriouh et al. 2017a). The effects of
33 biofouling formation in a PBR include a reduction in solar radiation inside the PBR,
34 poorer culture quality, a lower production rate and an increase in the process cost; this is
35 especially the case for closed PBRs (O. Zerriouh et al. 2019). To avoid all the above, and
36 to develop an effective closed PBR, it is crucial to find a new transparent anti-fouling
37 material that is also non-toxic.

38 Nowadays, there are two main methods employed to tackle marine organism fouling –
39 not allowing the foulant to attach in the first place or degrading it once it has attached
40 (Banerjee, Pangule, and Kane 2011). In terms of degrading the biofilm, it is assumed
41 that these foulants can be destroyed using a combination of proteases and glycosylases
42 (Kristensen et al. 2008) due to the proteinaceous and polysaccharide characteristics of
43 these components, which are mostly present in the initial adhesion step (Callow and
44 Callow 2000). However, there are certain aspects that complicate the application of this
45 technique when attempting to build an efficient closed PBR, such as the activity of the
46 enzymes over time, their degradation and their stability (Olsen et al. 2007; Zerriouh et
47 al. 2017a). On the other hand, numerous methods had tried to change the surface
48 properties of the PBR, for instance the charge or the physicochemical and mechanical
49 properties, thereby preventing initial foulant attachment. In recent years, research
50 methods have focused mainly on manipulating the physicochemical and mechanical

51 attributes that affect how marine creatures interact with the surface (Banerjee et al.
52 2011; Krishnan, Weinman, and Ober 2008). Functionalizing surfaces with very
53 hydrophilic poly (ethylene glycol) (PEG) is one of the key tactics. When foulants are
54 prevented from adhering to hydrophilic surfaces, attached species are more easily
55 removed from hydrophobic polymer-based coatings such fluoropolymers and
56 poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) (Andruzzi et al. 2004; Krishnan et al. 2006, 2008; Park
57 et al. 2010; Schumacher et al. 2007). That is why amphiphilic copolymers, formed by
58 both hydrophilic and hydrophobic functional groups, attract attention - this dual
59 behaviour weakens the microorganisms' interaction with the surface because their
60 adhesion becomes energetically unfavourable (Gudipati et al. 2004, 2005). Due to the
61 negative effects, both environmental and economic (Maréchal and Hellio 2009; Schultz
62 et al. 2011), associated with biofouling formation on ship hulls, researchers have
63 historically concentrated on creating novel methods or coatings to prevent this process
64 (Camós Noguier et al. 2017b; Gevaux et al. 2019). Nevertheless, other businesses are
65 also adversely affected by (micro)organism attachment, such as desalination
66 infrastructure, renewable energies, aquaculture and marine sensors (Delauney,
67 Compère, and Lehaitre 2010; Védie et al. 2021). The problem for the latter industries is
68 also shared by the microalgae cultivation sector, namely, that in addition to the
69 materials needing to prevent biofouling formation, they must also be transparent.
70 To date, there are few studies focused on avoiding microalgae adhesion on PBRs' inner
71 walls (Ozkan and Berberoglu 2013b; Soriano-Jerez et al. 2021; Wang et al. 2017;
72 Zeriouh et al. 2019), especially marine microalgae, since most of them have been
73 carried out on diatoms and freshwater microalgae (Ozkan and Berberoglu 2013b; Sekar
74 et al. 2004; Stanley and Callow 2007). Moreover, these studies show that the surfaces

75 with the lowest microalgae cell adhesion are not transparent (Soriano-Jerez et al. 2021;
76 Zeriouh et al. 2019), so they cannot be used to build an efficient closed PBR.
77 The aim of this work is to test the antibiofouling efficiency of different PDMS-based
78 coatings mixed with PEG-based additives in preventing microalgae cell adhesion, and
79 to select at least one of them. The coating must also be highly transparent in order to
80 build efficient closed PBRs. In this study, several PDMS/PEG coatings were prepared
81 and placed at the bottom of a 35 L open PBR in which the marine microalgae
82 *Nannochloropsis gaditana* (*N. gaditana*) was cultivated for 8 months, thus testing their
83 antibiofouling efficiency. These coatings were prepared in two thicknesses to check if
84 this parameter affects the ability to prevent microalgae cell adhesion. The biofouling
85 formation was monitored visually by taking a series of photos and then quantified at the
86 end of the experiment. To better understand the cell-coating interactions, extended
87 Derjaguin, Landau, Verwey, Overbeek (XDLVO) theory was also applied. Although
88 this theory was principally developed to predict bacterial adhesion (Perni, Preedy, and
89 Prokopovich 2014), it has also been applied satisfactorily to microalgae cell interactions
90 (Ozkan and Berberoglu 2013a; Zeriouh et al. 2017b; Zeriouh et al. 2017a).

91 **2. Materials and Methods**

92 2.1. Transparent fouling-release coatings

93 Seven different fouling-release coatings based on a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)
94 matrix were tested. PDMS, which provides hydrophobic properties, was mixed with
95 additives based on polyethylene-glycol (PEG) to provide hydrophilic character. The
96 seven different additives tested were: CMS-626, DBE-224, DBE-311, DBE-814, DBE-
97 821 and DBE-C25, all of them from Gelest (Pennsylvania, United States), and OFX-
98 0400 from Dow Corning (Michigan, United States). The PDMS used was Sylgard™
99 184, again supplied by Dow Corning (Michigan, United States). Sylgard™ 184,

100 Hempasil X₃® (Hempel A/S, Denmark) and borosilicate glass (Normax®, Portugal)
101 were used as controls.

102 The fouling-release coatings (FRCs) were prepared as follows: briefly, Sylgard 184
103 (PDMS:crosslinker 10:1 w/w) was mixed with each additive (4% w/w), using xylene
104 (Chem-Lab, Zedelgem, Belgium) as solvent. The mixture was placed in a vacuum to
105 remove all the bubbles and then it was applied over a 76x52 mm borosilicate glass
106 bracket (Normax®, Portugal) using a micrometre-adjustable film applicator (3580/3
107 Universal micrometre applicator, Neurtek, Spain) to control the FRC's thickness.

108 It is known that coating thickness plays an important role in removing fouling
109 organisms from FRCs (Chaudhury et al. 2005). In order to evaluate if this parameter is
110 crucial to avoid microalgae cell attachment, two different thicknesses (120 and 240 µm)
111 were tested. This parameter is especially relevant given that, if the thickness increases a
112 lot, the transparency decreases.

113 The transmittance of the coatings was obtained by measuring the UV-Vis spectra, as
114 described elsewhere (Larena et al. 2002), using a Helios Omega-UV Spectrophotometer
115 (Thermo Scientific, UK).

116 2.2. Microalgae, culture conditions and experimental setup

117 The Andalusian Institute of Marine Sciences (CSIC) contributed the marine microalga
118 *Nannochloropsis gaditana* B-3 from its Marine Culture Collection. The inoculum was
119 grown at a temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ in 5 L vessels using 32W fluorescent lamps, which
120 provided an average irradiance of $100 \mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ on to the culture vessel surface. The
121 contents of the vessel were agitated by filter-sterilized air sparging, which was injected
122 through a sparger nozzle at an aeration rate of $0.5 \text{ v v}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. N-Optimized Algal
123 (Camacho-Rodríguez et al. 2013) was used as the culture medium; this was prepared

124 from natural filter-sterilized (0.22 μm Whatman GF/F 47 mm, Maidstone, UK)
125 Mediterranean seawater (at 30 psu).
126 A 35-L indoor raceway PBR was used as the culture system to test the antibiofouling
127 properties of the FRCs. Curved baffles placed at either end of the raceway ensured
128 uniform flow through the bend and reduced the formation of dead zones. A paddlewheel
129 with six flat blades was used to move the culture at a flow rate of $12.5 \pm 0.4 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. The
130 fundamental tracer method was employed to measure the flow rate (Sanchez et al.,
131 2000). The RW-PBR was illuminated at an average irradiance of $135 \mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ on the
132 culture surface under a 12:12 h light/dark cycle. A 4π sensor (QSL-2101; Biospherical
133 Instruments) was used to measure the irradiance. The pH was kept at 8.0 by
134 automatically injecting fine bubbles of pure carbon dioxide through a tiny microporous
135 gas diffuser at a rate of $0.1 \text{ v v}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. In order to favour the diffusion and mixing of the
136 nutrients and cells, filter-sterilized air was injected into the culture through a sparger
137 nozzle at an aeration rate of $0.5 \text{ v v}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. The air and carbon dioxide diffuser were
138 positioned beneath and directly behind the paddlewheel. The culture was kept at a
139 constant temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The coatings were placed at the bottom of the PBR,
140 at the end of the opposite channel (straight-section) from the paddlewheel and the air
141 and CO_2 injection. Thus, samples were 243.4 cm away of them, in order to ensure
142 homogeneous fluid dynamics for all the coatings, as shown in Figure 1a, there was not
143 observed any influence of paddlewheel and gas injection. Three replicates of each
144 coating and thickness were tested, excepting for Hempasil X₃® and glass that were
145 tested with duplicates and four replicates for each thickness, respectively. Figure 1b
146 shows a scheme of the raceway used while Figures 1c and 1d detail the PBR
147 dimensions. Figures 1b-d were created using FreeCad software. The PBR and coatings

148 were sterilized using a neutralization process with sodium thiosulfate after being rinsed
149 with sodium hypochlorite solution (Andersen 2005).

150 The N-optimized Algal culture medium, as prepared by Camacho-Rodríguez et al. (
151 2013), was used as the basis, with a N/P ratio of 15; this was achieved by changing the
152 phosphorous concentration (Soriano-Jerez et al. 2021). The experiment was inoculated
153 with exponentially proliferating cells at an initial biomass concentration of 0.12 ± 0.01 g
154 L^{-1} and an initial pH of 7.8. The experiment started with a batch culture phase. When
155 the culture reached stationary growth, the continuous phase began. At this point, new
156 medium was fed in a constant metered rate to provide the desired dilution.

157 2.3. Monitoring microalgal growth

158 The culture's biomass concentration (C_b , $g L^{-1}$) was determined by applying a
159 calibration curve between C_b and OD_{540} , as reported previously (Camacho-Rodríguez et
160 al. 2013; Soriano-Jerez et al. 2021). For this measurement, a Helios Omega UV-Vis
161 spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) was used. To record the photosynthetic
162 efficiency of Photosystem II (F_v/F_m) for the freely suspended cells in the culture broth,
163 a pulse amplitude modulation (PAM) chlorophyll fluorometer (PAM-2500 chlorophyll
164 fluorometer, Heinz Walz GmbH) was employed, as previously described (López-
165 Rosales et al. 2014). Each determination was made in triplicate and the average result
166 was used. To make up for evaporation losses, distilled water was added to the open
167 PBR.

168 2.4. Monitoring microalgal attachment

169 Cell attachment was evaluated visually over time by taking a series of photographs. The
170 surfaces were temporarily removed from the PBR, a photograph was taken of them, and
171 then they were returned to the bottom of the PBR. The cell adhesion on the surfaces was
172 quantified once the cultivation experiments were finished (after 8 months). The surfaces

173 were carefully extracted from the PBR and placed in a flask to rinse them with sterile
174 Mediterranean seawater, under very low agitation (concretely, 50 rpm in an orbital
175 shaker for 30 s); this was done to remove non-adherent cells and contaminants. The
176 microalgae cell adhesion on the surfaces was quantified by measuring the chlorophyll *a*
177 (Chl *a*) fluorescence of the attached microalgae cells, as previously described (Soriano-
178 Jerez et al. 2021; Zeriouh et al. 2017b). The temporary evaluation of the fouling
179 formation on the surfaces has been carried out measuring the percentage of fouling
180 intensity (microalga cells, salt deposition, nutrients, EPS, etc.) on each surface by photo
181 processing with free ImageJ software using a 2-D percent coverage measurement.

182 2.5. Supernatant characterization

183 The American Public Health Association's 4500-P and 4500-N spectrophotometric
184 procedures for the evaluation of water were used to measure the phosphate and nitrate
185 concentrations in the supernatants (American Public Health Association, American
186 Water Works Association, and Federation of Sewage & Industrial Wastes Associations
187 1995). All determinations were performed in triplicate and the average value was used.

188 2.6. Toxicity assessment

189 The toxicity for the microalga *N. gaditana* of the different tested coatings was evaluated
190 by immersing each one in a petri plate (90 mm diameter) under static conditions. The
191 control consisted of a petri plate with no coating inside.

192 The procedure to evaluate the toxicity of the surface was the same as used by Soriano-
193 Jerez et al. (2021). Briefly, the petri plates were inoculated with the marine microalga *N.*
194 *gaditana* at a biomass concentration of 0.16 g L⁻¹. Inoculum was at exponential growth
195 phase. In the petri plates, cells were grown in batch mode for 15 days under static
196 conditions, with an incident irradiance of 65 μE m⁻² s⁻¹ (12h/12h light-dark regime), at a
197 temperature of 25 ± 2°C and using the culture medium N-Optimized Algal (Camacho-

198 Rodríguez et al. 2013). The biomass concentration (g L^{-1}) and the Fv/Fm monitoring in
199 each culture were carried out using the same procedures described in Section 2.3. The
200 coatings' toxicity was evaluated at the beginning and at the end of the culture by: (i) the
201 maximum photochemical photosystem II (Fv/Fm) yield; and (ii) the rapid light curve
202 (RLC) method obtained by measure the photosynthesis-light response curves (White
203 and Critchley, 1999). Following a 30-minute period of dark-cell acclimation, the Fv/Fm
204 was measured, and then the RLCs were acquired with a 27 second exposure at each
205 actinic light level. A complete RLC was obtained by fitting the rETR vs E data to the
206 Eilers and Peeters' model (Eilers and Peeters, 1988) using the photosynthetic activity
207 calculated as the relative electron transport rate (rETR) at incremental irradiances, E (0,
208 10, 60, 140, 242, 411, 661, 997, 1381 and 1963 $\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The
209 photosynthetic parameters that were estimated were α (photosynthetic rate in the light-
210 limited region), E_k (the saturating irradiance) and rETR_{max} (the relative maximum
211 electron transport rate). All experiments were carried out in duplicate.

212 2.7. XDLVO approach to the microalgal adhesion on the FRCs

213 In order to apply the XDLVO theory to check if this model is useful in predicting *N.*
214 *gaditana* cell adhesion on the FRCs, the microalgal adhesion and contact angles were
215 measured. As the culture media base is Mediterranean seawater, which has a very high
216 ionic strength ($I = 680 \text{ mM}$), the microalgae cell zeta potential and the surface potential
217 is very low and constant, whatever the material (Zerriouh et al. 2017b). For this reason,
218 the physicochemical properties of the microalgae surface, as the zeta potential, and the
219 surface potential data were used, as in Zerriouh et al. (2017b). In this model, the total
220 interaction energy (G_{TOT}) is a function of the distance between the interacting surfaces,
221 with a negative G_{TOT} value indicating adhesion while a positive one indicates repulsion
222 between the surfaces (Ozkan and Berberoglu 2013b; Zerriouh et al. 2017b). In

223 supplementary material it can be seen in more detail the equations and the parameters'

224 value used in XDLVO theory. Briefly:

$$225 \quad G_{TOT}(d) = G_{LW}(d) + G_{EL}(d) + G_{Ab}(d) \quad [1]$$

226 where:

$$227 \quad G_{LW}(d) = \frac{-A}{6} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{a}{d} + \frac{a}{d+2 \cdot a} \right) + \text{Ln} \left(\frac{d}{d+2 \cdot a} \right) \right] \quad [2]$$

$$228 \quad G_{EL}(d) = \pi \cdot \varepsilon \cdot a \cdot (\psi_m^2 + \psi_s^2) \cdot \left[\frac{2 \cdot \psi_m \cdot \psi_s}{\psi_m^2 + \psi_s^2} \cdot \text{Ln} \left(\frac{1 + \exp(-\kappa \cdot d)}{1 - \exp(-\kappa \cdot d)} \right) + \right. \\ 229 \quad \left. \text{Ln}(1 - \exp(-2 \cdot \kappa \cdot d)) \right]$$

$$230 \quad [3]$$

$$231 \quad G_{AB}(d) = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot a \cdot \lambda \cdot \Delta G_{adh}^{AB} \cdot \exp \left(\frac{d_0 - d}{\lambda} \right) \quad [4]$$

232 Being:

233 G_{AB} the acid-base component; G_{EL} the electrostatic component; and G_{LW} the lifshitz-van
234 der Waals component of total energy interaction (G_{TOT}).

235 A is the Hamaker's constant (J); a equivalent radius of the algal cell (m); d separation
236 distance between two surfaces (m); d_0 minimum separation distance between two
237 surfaces (m); k_B Boltzmann's constant (J K⁻¹).

238 ΔG_{adh} is the change in free energy (J m⁻²) refers to adhesion; ε the dielectric constant of
239 culture medium, i.e. seawater (F m⁻¹); κ the inverse of double layer thickness (m⁻¹); λ is
240 the correlation length, i.e., gyration radius of water molecules in a solution; and ψ the
241 surface potential (V).

242 It has to take into account that the subscripts: m refers to microalga, and s refers to

243 substrate.

244

245 2.8. Statistical analyses

246 The significant difference analysis was performed using a one-way analysis of variance
247 (ANOVA) test. In order to determine the effect on microalga cell adhesion of the
248 additive type (factor A) and coating thickness (factor B), multifactor ANOVA was
249 performed. Another multifactor ANOVA was carried out to determine the effect of the
250 additive type (factor A), immersion time (factor B) and their interaction (A-B) on
251 percentage fouling intensity. A 5.0% significance level threshold ($p < 0.05$) was
252 considered as statistically significant differences. Fisher's least significant difference
253 (LSD) method was used to discriminate between the means at the 95.0% confidence
254 level. Statgraphics Centurion XVII (version 17.2.04) statistical software (2014,
255 Statpoint Technologies, Inc., Warrenton, VA) was used to analyse the statistical data.
256 Minitab (v19) software has been used to calculate the p-value of each surface
257 comparing with a surface control (glass) at each period of immersion by Dunnet
258 method. Differences that exceeded the 0.05 p-value threshold were considered
259 statistically significant.

260

261 3. Results and discussion

262 3.1. Transmittance of coatings

263 Table 1 shows the transmittance of each surface with a thickness of 120 μm and 240 μm
264 at 780 nm, before the immersion (clean surface) and after 8 months immersion in the
265 marine microalga *N. gaditana* culture, (once the surfaces have been gently cleaned after
266 being immersed for 8 months) to evaluate the durability of coatings' transmittance. As
267 expected, the commercial paint Hempasil X3® has a null transmittance due to its
268 opaque characteristic. In contrast, PDMS without the additive has a high transmittance

269 because of its high transparency (Sales et al. 2021; Shih et al. 2006). It should be noted
270 that the surface transparency can change with temperature (Sales et al. 2021). However,
271 in Table 1, one can observe that all the clean PDMS/PEG-based coatings have a lower
272 transmittance than glass (100%), reducing to 50% for the coating made with DBE-C25,
273 and near to 75% in the case of CMS-626. Moreover, in all cases, the transmittance
274 decreases with thickness. Therefore, inside a closed PBR covered with these types of
275 coatings, the internal irradiance will be lower than in a closed PBR constructed of glass.
276 It is noteworthy that the coating made with the DBE-311 additive presented a very high
277 transmittance, above 90%, even at a thickness of 240 μm . In addition, all surfaces
278 present a similar transmittance after 8 months immersion in the marine culture to time 0
279 (clean surface), except coatings elaborated with additives DBE-224 and DBE-821
280 which decreased about 50% (see table 1). The coating with the additive DBE-311
281 maintained a transmittance higher than 90%.

282 3.2. Culture and macronutrient kinetics

283 The biofouling test consisted of immersing the coatings in a *N. gaditana* culture over a
284 long period (8 months). The experiment started as a batch culture to acclimate the cells
285 to the new conditions inside the PBR. After 18 days, the culture reached the stationary
286 phase so the continuous mode was started at a dilution rate of 0.17 day^{-1} . Figure 2
287 shows the culture's evolution over the 8 months for the following variables: the biomass
288 concentration (C_b , g/L), the photosynthetic efficiency of Photosystem II (Fv/Fm), and
289 the consumed kinetics of the nitrates (NO_3^- , mM) and phosphates (PO_4^{3-} , μM). As
290 expected, the phosphate concentration decreased quickly, with practically all of it being
291 consumed, which is reflected by the biomass concentration increasing. The biomass
292 concentration was close to 1.4 g/L on reaching the stationary state, stabilizing at around
293 1.2 g/L during continuous mode, while the Fv/Fm did not change significantly

294 throughout the culture period, being close to 0.6 for the entire time, which is indicative
295 of healthy cells (Soriano-Jerez et al. 2021; Zerriouh et al. 2019).

296 3.3. Cell adhesion

297 Figure 3 shows the evolution of fouling formation on surfaces at times 0 (Figure 3a), 30
298 days (Figure 3b), 3 months (Figure 3c), 6 months (Figure 3d) and 8 months (Figure 3e)
299 of evaluation in the PBR. In Figure 3f it has been included name and position of each
300 sample. The evolution of fouling intensity on each surface over time was illustrated in
301 figure 3g for coatings with 120 μm thickness and in figure 3h for coatings with 240 μm
302 thickness. No great difference in fouling formation between the two thicknesses tested
303 can be appreciated. After 30 days, it can be observed that fouling formation is very low
304 (see figure 3b, 3g and 3h), just glass presented a fouling intensity higher than 30%,
305 followed by CMS-626 and PDMS (about 20% and 16%, respectively). However, after 3
306 months there were some differences between coatings (figure 3c, 3g and 3h). Some of
307 them presented low fouling formation, lower than 30% for DBE-224, OFX-0400, DBE-
308 C25, DBE-311 and Hemptasil X3®; while others presented moderate fouling formation,
309 between 50% – 80%, for DBE-821, PDMS and CMS-626. At this time of culture, glass
310 presented high fouling formation (higher than 80%), so all of the tested coatings are a
311 good alternative to glass for building efficient closed-PBRs, excepting coatings CMS-
312 626 and DBE-821 due to there is no statistical difference between them and glass (p-
313 value>0.05, see Table S2). After 6 months immersion, it can be seen that the difference
314 in fouling were higher (see figures 3e, 3g and 3h). Some coatings presented low fouling
315 formation intensity; lower than 20%, such as OFX-0400, DBE-311 and Hemptasil X3®.
316 Others presented moderate fouling formation, between 50% and 80% (DBE-814, DBE-
317 224, DBE-C25 and CMS-626), while the rest presented high fouling formation, DBE-
318 821, PDMS and glass showed fouling formation higher than 80%. Finally, after 8

319 months of immersion (See figures 3f, 3g, and 3h) the only surfaces that show a low
320 fouling formation were DBE-311 and Hempasil X3® (lower than 20%); OFX-0400 and
321 DBE-C25 presented moderate biofouling formation (around 50%); and DBE-814, DBE-
322 224 DBE-821, PDMS, CMS-626 and glass presented high fouling formation intensity
323 (higher than 80%). Statistically, there has been no significant difference between
324 coatings CMS-626, DBE-821, PDMS and glass during the first 6 months of culture (see
325 Table S2). However, after 8 months of culture there was no statistically significant
326 difference with glass except for coatings DBE-311, DBE-C25, OFX-0400 and Hempasil
327 X3®.

328 Figure 3i shows the cell adhesion quantification (cells/mm²) on each surface after 8
329 months of immersion in the non-flagellated *N. gaditana* marine microalga culture. All
330 the surfaces showed less cell adhesion than glass, even the PDMS control. DBE-311
331 and Hempasil X3® were the surfaces with the lowest microalga cell adhesion, followed
332 by OFX-0400 and DBE-C25, which corresponded with the surfaces with lowest fouling
333 formation intensity. However, a discrepancy between the results obtained of fouling
334 intensity and cell adhesion was observed: while CMS-626, PDMS and DBE-821
335 presented a fouling formation similar than glass, the cell adhesion for these coatings
336 was lower than glass. It could be due to the presence of foulants substances, such as salt,
337 nutrients, etc., which are taken into account in fouling formation intensity, but do not
338 necessarily imply that final microalgae cells adhesion can be predicted based on their
339 presence exclusively. It has to be mention that one glass sample (row 3, column 7) was
340 discarded and not taken into account to calculate the cell adhesion and fouling intensity
341 average because it was not possible that after 8 months immersion glass remains with
342 practically no cell adhesion (Zerriouh et al. 2017a). Moreover, some parts of DBE-C25
343 (row 5, column 1), glass (row 3, column 2) and glass (row 5, column 4) were neglected

344 to calculate the cell adhesion because as it can be seen in Figure 3e, it was very low.
345 However, it was not due to the good antibiofouling surface properties, but adhered cells
346 could have been detached as typically occurs in a cyclic way in dense mature biofilms (
347 Zeriouh et al. 2017b) or even, this discrepancy between samples could be due to
348 retraction phenomena (Vena et al. 2021) observed in all surfaces when the fouling
349 adhesion is low. When fouling formation is not very heavy, retraction is observed on all
350 surfaces, even on glass. So, this phenomenon was observed on all surfaces until 3
351 months of immersion. After that time, heavy biofouling was formed over some surfaces
352 and, on that, retraction phenomena was not observed on them.

353 Considering the evolution of this biofouling formation over time, even though DBE-311
354 is clearly the best option (due to its low fouling), all of them are a better option for
355 building a closed PBR than glass. With regard to the culture time period, DBE-224
356 might be a good option for a culture period of less than 3 months while DBE-C25
357 might be suitable for a 1-month culture. This difference in cell adhesion could be due to
358 the adhesion strength between the surface and water molecules, which is responsible for
359 the formation of the hydration layer. This adhesion strength is influenced by the amount
360 of PEG on the surface when the additive diffuses and/or reorganises towards the coating
361 surface. Moreover, this loss in antibiofouling efficacy over time might be due to the
362 additive being released into the seawater (Camós Noguer et al. 2017b), decreasing the
363 amount of PEG within the coating and causing reduced adhesion strength between the
364 coating and the water molecules.

365 Regarding to the fouling intensity seven groups can be distinguished statistically for
366 additive type (see table 2). Each group presents significant differences, with $p < 0.05$:
367 the first group with the lowest fouling intensity formed by DBE-311 and Hempasil X3®
368 (4%), followed by the second group formed by OFX-0400 (15%). The third group

369 includes DBE-C25 (23%) and the fourth group DBE-224 (32%). The fifth group
370 comprises DBE-814, DBE-821 and PDMS (around 45%). The next group is composed
371 of PDMS and CMS-626 (around 50%); and the group with the highest fouling intensity
372 is formed by CMS-626 and glass (58%). Nonetheless, five adhesion groups can be
373 distinguished statistically on microalga cell adhesion (see table 2) - the group with the
374 most adhesion corresponding to the glass control (close to 25 000 cells/mm²), the
375 second highest corresponding to the PDMS control and the DBE-821 coating, having a
376 cell adhesion of around 15 000 cells/mm². The third group comprises CMS-626 and
377 DBE-224, which have a cell adhesion close to 10 000 cells/mm². The fourth is made up
378 of DBE-814 and DBE-C25, while the last group, with the lowest cell adhesion,
379 correspond to those coatings with the DBE-311 and OFX-0400 additives; Hempasil
380 X3® is also in this last group. Factor thickness has no statistically significant influence
381 on cell adhesion. However, factor time has statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) on fouling
382 intensity and can be distinguished 4 groups: the first one is time 0 of immersion, which
383 means that surfaces are clean (0%), the second one is 1 month (9%), the third is 3
384 months (36%) and the last group comprises 6 and 8 months (60%). Therefore, to
385 analyse (i) the effect of type of additive (factor A) and thickness (factor B) on microalga
386 cell adhesion and (ii) the effect of type of additive (factor A) and immersion time (factor
387 B) and interactions (A-B) on fouling intensity, a multifactor ANOVA was carried out.
388 Type of additive had statistically significant effect on microalga cell adhesion at the
389 95.0% confidence level ($p < 0.05$) but not the thickness. However, on fouling intensity
390 both factors and interactions had a statistically significant effect at the 95.0%
391 confidence level ($p < 0.05$). The most important contributions to fouling intensity
392 corresponded to the immersion time (76.0%), the type of additive (20.3%) and the type
393 of additive interaction with immersion time (3.7%).

394

395 3.4. Toxicity assessment

396 After 15 days of culture, the average biomass concentration in cultures was 0.71 ± 0.06 g
397 L^{-1} and a Fv/Fm of 0.617 ± 0.006 (figure S1 in supplementary material). Table 3 shows
398 the Fv/Fm and photosynthetic parameters (α , $rETR_{max}$ and E_k) of the inoculum (initial
399 state) and at the end of the batch culture. The Fv/Fm obtained at the end of the batch
400 culture was higher than 0.6 in all cases which indicates that cells are healthy.

401 Considering the photosynthetic parameters, the photosynthetic rate in the light-limited
402 region (α) at the end of the batch culture did not vary significantly in comparison with
403 the inoculum. However, the relative maximum electron transport rate ($rETR_{max}$) and the
404 saturating irradiance (E_k) increased considerably 158% and 174%, respectively. As it
405 can be seen, the photosynthetic parameters of the cultures where coatings were
406 immersed did not vary significantly compared to the control culture, which indicates
407 that these coatings are not toxic to *N. gaditana*.

408 3.5. XDLVO approach

409 The behaviour of the coatings changes over time when they are in contact with water.
410 This is due to the PEG interacting with the water molecules (O'Brien and Paranjape
411 2021). Hence, it is very important to study such behaviour: (i) prior to immersion (or
412 before the interaction with the water); (ii) after the immersion, when the most
413 hydrophilic state is reached; and (iii) at the end of the experiment, when the biofouling
414 has formed on them.

415 Figure 4 shows the EL, LW, AB, and total interaction energy for the *N. gaditana*-FRC
416 (Figs. 4a-4g and 4i), *N. gaditana*-PDMS (Fig. 4h) and *N. gaditana*-glass (Fig. 4j)
417 systems as a function of the separation distance before the surface modification
418 resulting from the interaction with the water droplets (O'Brien and Paranjape 2021).

419 Figure 4a to Figure 4i indicate that, at distances very close to the surface (less than 3
420 nm), the total interaction energy is negative, so the cells should adhere to all these
421 surfaces. However, one can also observe that there is a maximum total energy
422 interaction at around 4 nm, meaning there is a minimum repulsion force here (Perni et
423 al. 2014). Consequently, the total interaction energy is positive - the surface should
424 repel cells at this distance. However, if a microalgae cell with a very high kinetic energy
425 moves parallel to the surface at this distance, it could attach itself. Nevertheless, this
426 energy would have to be extremely high given that the total interaction energy is very
427 high (around 100 – 200 k_bT); indeed, it is practically impossible for a microalgae cell in
428 this system to have such a high kinetic energy value, so the *N. gaditana* cells should not
429 adhere to these surfaces due to the significant energy barrier formed around the
430 coatings. In the case of the *N. gaditana*-glass system (Fig. 4j), one can see that the curve
431 shape matches the values obtained by Zeriouh et al. (2017b) for the same system. The
432 total energy interaction is positive at distances very close to the surface so the cells will
433 not attach to the glass. However, if one zooms in on this figure (dashed purple line), one
434 can observe a secondary minimum for the total interaction energy at around $-20 k_bT$, in
435 our case, at distances of 7 nm, and in the case of Zeriouh et al. at 5.8 nm (2017b). This
436 means that, if a microalgae cell with a kinetic energy higher than $23 k_bT$ were moving at
437 this distance from the glass, it would probably not adhere to the surface at this
438 secondary minimum. Figure 5 shows the EL, LW, AB and total interaction energy for
439 the *N. gaditana*- FRC (Fig. 5a-5g and 5i), *N. gaditana*-PDMS (Fig. 5h) and *N.*
440 *gaditana*-glass (Fig. 5j) systems as a function of the separation distance, after the
441 surface modification resulting from the interaction with the water droplets (O'Brien and
442 Paranjape 2021). Because these coatings are additive surfaces, when they come into
443 contact with water, they change their surface properties due to the interaction between

444 the PEG and the water; this is the reason for the differences between Figures 4 and 5.
445 One can also see some differences between Figures 5a to 5i, whereas Figures 4a to 4i
446 are all very similar. This is because all the FRCs act like PDMS before the surfaces
447 interact with the water (Fig. 4h). The only difference between Figures 4a to 4i is the
448 maximum value although all of them are between 100 – 200 k_bT . This difference might
449 be due to a small amount of PEG being present on the surface. Nevertheless, after a few
450 seconds, the PEG in the coatings interacts with the water and the coatings begin to
451 behave differently due to the varying amounts of PEG, the size, the molecular weight,
452 the structure, and the additive's diffusion rate, etc. (Camós Noguer et al. 2017a). Hence
453 the differences observed between Figures 5a to 5i, where the coatings made with the
454 DBE-814 (Fig. 5a), DBE-224 (Fig. 5b), OFX-0400 (Fig. 5d), DBE-C25 (Fig. 5e) and
455 DBE-311 (Fig. 5f) additives do not present a secondary maximum in total energy
456 interaction. For these 5 surfaces, all the total energy interactions are positive, so no cell
457 adhesion should occur even if the microalgae cell moves with an extremely high kinetic
458 energy very close to the surface. The surfaces corresponding to Figures 5c, 5g, 5h and 5i
459 present negative total interaction energy values at distances very close to the surface
460 but, again, there is a very high maximum value at around 4 nm (approx. 120 – 250 k_bT);
461 thus, it is practically impossible for a microalgae cell to adhere to these surfaces. This
462 might be explained by the high interaction forces between these types of coatings and
463 water, which form a hydration layer on the coating, inhibiting cell adhesion. Therefore,
464 according to XDLVO theory these coatings and Hempasil X3® must have good
465 antibiofouling properties due to their high energy at distances very close to the surface
466 (DBE-814, DBE-224, OFX-0400, DBE-C25 and DBE-311) or the high energy barrier
467 in its vicinity (Hempasil X3®, DBE-821, PDMS, CMS-626). However, this did not
468 occur in the case of the *N.gaditana*-glass system (Fig. 5j) because glass, which is not a

469 functionalized surface, does not interact with water over time – that is why there is no
470 difference between Figures 4j and 5j.

471 Figure 6 shows the EL, LW, AB and total interaction energy for the *N. gaditana*- FRC
472 (Figs. 6a-6g and 6i), *N. gaditana*-PDMS (Fig. 6h) and *N. gaditana*-glass (Fig. 6j)
473 systems as a function of the separation distance after 8 months of immersion in the
474 marine microalgae *N. gaditana* culture. In this case, one can observe that all the surfaces
475 have undergone a modification in their interaction energies. For all the surfaces (the
476 PDMS-PEG coatings, PDMS, Hempasil X3® and glass), the total interaction energy is
477 positive at distances very close to the surface, so there should be no more adhered cells
478 on them. However, in all cases, there is a secondary minimum at 7 nm from the surface.
479 Consequently, if a microalga cell is moving at this distance with a kinetic energy lower
480 than the total interaction energy value at the secondary minimum, it could adhere to the
481 surface, as in the *N. gaditana*-glass system at time 0 (Figure 4j).

482 Therefore, according to XDLVO theory, these PEG/PDMS coatings should have good
483 antibiofouling properties due to the high value of the total energy interaction at
484 distances very close to the transparent coatings for the case of DBE-814, DBE-224,
485 OFX-0400, DBE-C25 and DBE-311, or due to the high energy barrier in its vicinity in
486 the case of Hempasil X3®, DBE-821, PDMS and CMS-626. This high energy value
487 makes difficult for a microalga cell to approach the surface, so it is practically
488 impossible for the cell to attach to it. This is what happened at time 0. However, after 8
489 months, some cells have adhered to the transparent coatings (Figure 3e and 3g). This
490 might be explained by the formation of the conditioning film (Soriano-Jerez et al. 2021;
491 Zeriouh et al. 2017b) or even due to the fluid dynamics of the PBR, which is not taken
492 into account in the XDLVO theory (Kichouh-Aiadi et al. 2021). It is possible that,
493 initially, the microalga cells (at least the *N. gaditana* cells) do not adhere to these

494 coatings. Nevertheless, the exopolymeric substances secreted by the microalgae, such as
495 proteins and polysaccharides, could adhere to them, forming the conditioning film (thus
496 modifying the surfaces) and, after this has occurred, some of the microalga cells could
497 adhere to them (Zerriouh et al. 2017a). Furthermore, one must take into account that the
498 PEG-based copolymer additives might be released from the coatings over time (Camós
499 Noguer et al. 2017a, 2017b) so if the amount of additive decreases within the coating,
500 its antibiofouling properties will diminish as well. This variation in surfaces' properties
501 can be seen in the difference patterns represented in figure 5 and 6. The interaction
502 between a *N. gaditana* cell and the surface is not the same for time zero (figure 5) and
503 after 8 months of immersion in the culture (figure 6). Besides, no correlation has been
504 found between the total energy interaction and the antibiofouling properties, so the
505 XDLVO theory is not used to preselect a FRC as the best antibiofouling properties
506 coating, among all tested. XDLVO model showed the good antibiofouling properties of
507 the clean coatings and the variation of the interaction forces of the surfaces after 8
508 months of immersion in a *N. gaditana* culture, so it is a good model to interpret the
509 interaction forces between a microalgae cell and the surface in a particular moment. But
510 according to others authors (Kichouh-Aiadi et al. 2021), the model is not enough to
511 predict the biofouling formation on a surface over time.

512 **4. Conclusions**

513 PEG/PDMS-based coatings with 4% w/w PEG-based copolymers are a good alternative
514 for avoiding *N. gaditana* cell adhesion. However, the best option, among all tested, to
515 build an efficient-closed PBR is DBE-311 due to its high transmittance and low cell
516 adhesion after 8 months of immersion in the *N. gaditana* culture, period after which it
517 also maintains its transmittance higher than 90%.

518 The XDLVO theory indicates that these clean PEG/PDMS coatings would avoid *N.*
519 *gaditana* cell adhesion due to the high value of the total energy interaction at distances
520 very close to the transparent coatings or to the high energy barrier at its vicinity.
521 However, these coatings showed microalgal cell adhesion after 8 months of immersion,
522 excepting DBE-311. Surfaces properties at this time, according to the XDLVO theory,
523 had been modified and were favourable to *N. gaditana* cell adhesion. Therefore,
524 XDLVO theory is useful to explain the interaction forces between microalgae cell and
525 the surface at a certain moment in time, but it should be complemented with models that
526 be able to predict the formation of the conditioning film and the contribution of the fluid
527 dynamics of the PBR over time.

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533 **Declaration of interests**

534 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
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692 **Figure captions**

693 **Figure 1.** (a) Coating position at the bottom of the PBR, (b) raceway scheme (c)
694 elevation and (d) profile (created with FreeCad software). The thickness of the PBR
695 pieces is 1 mm.

696 **Figure 2.** Freely suspended cell concentration of *N. gaditana* [C_b] (g/L), photosynthetic
697 efficiency of Photosystem II (Fv/Fm), nitrate concentration [NO_3^-] (mM) and phosphate
698 concentration [PO_4^{3-}] (μM) during the culture period.

699 **Figure 3.** Coating aspects (a) prior to immersion; (b) after 30 days of immersion; (c) after
700 3 months of immersion; (d) after 6 months of immersion; and (e) after 8 months of
701 immersion in a *N. gaditana* marine microalga culture. (f) Scheme of the coating positions:
702 orange is DBE-814, brown is DBE-224, red is Hempasil X3®, dark green is OFX-0400,
703 pink is DBE-C25, turquoise is DBE-311, blue is DBE-821, grey is PDM, green is CMS-
704 626 and black is glass. (g) Fouling formation intensity (%) over time on coatings with
705 120 μm . (h) Fouling formation intensity (%) over time on coatings with 240 μm . (i) Cell
706 adhesion (cells/mm^2) on each coating (and on glass) after 8 months of immersion in a *N.*
707 *gaditana* marine microalga culture.

708 **Figure 4.** Dynamics of the interaction energy (G, k_bT) predicted by the XDLVO model
709 for the *N. gaditana* – coating system (a) DBE-814, (b) DBE-224, (c) Hempasil X3®,
710 (d) OFX-0400, (e) DBE-C25, (f) DBE-311, (g) DBE-821, (h) PDMS, (i) CMS-626, and
711 (j) glass, before the water droplet change. Dashed brown lines indicate a zero-energy
712 value. Dashed purple lines indicate the zone where the zoom was carried out.

713 **Figure 5.** Dynamics of the interaction energy (G, k_bT) predicted by the XDLVO model
714 for the *N. gaditana* – coating systems: (a) DBE-814, (b) DBE-224, (c) Hempasil X3®,
715 (d) OFX-0400, (e) DBE-C25, (f) DBE-311, (g) DBE-821, (h) PDMS, (i) CMS-626, and
716 (j) glass, after the water contact angle change. Dashed brown lines indicate a zero-
717 energy value.

718 **Figure 6.** Dynamics of the interaction energy (G, k_bT) predicted by the XDLVO model
719 for the *N. gaditana* – coating systems: (a) DBE-814, (b) DBE-224, (c) Hempasil X3®,
720 (d) OFX-0400, (e) DBE-C25, (f) DBE-311, (g) DBE-821, (h) PDMS, (i) CMS-626, and
721 (j) glass, after 8 months of immersion. Dashed brown lines indicate a zero-energy value.
722

Figure 1

Figure 2.

DBE-814 120 μm	PDMS 240 μm	DBE-C25 120 μm	DBE-821 240 μm	DBE-311 120 μm	Hemipasil X3 120 μm	CMS-626 240 μm	GLASS
DBE-224 240 μm	CMS-626 240 μm	DBE-224 120 μm	DBE-814 240 μm	DBE-821 120 μm	OFX-0400 240 μm	PDMS 240 μm	DBE-C25 120 μm
Hemipasil X3 240 μm	GLASS	CMS-626 120 μm	PDMS 240 μm	OFX-0400 120 μm	DBE-C25 240 μm	GLASS	DBE-821 120 μm
OFX-0400 240 μm	OFX-0400 120 μm	DBE-814 120 μm	DBE-224 240 μm	CMS-626 120 μm	DBE-311 240 μm	Hemipasil X3 240 μm	PDMS 120 μm
DBE-C25 240 μm	DBE-821 120 μm	DBE-311 240 μm	GLASS	DBE-224 120 μm	DBE-814 240 μm	OFX-0400 120 μm	DBE-311 120 μm
DBE-311 240 μm	PDMS 120 μm	CMS-626 240 μm	OFX-0400 240 μm	DBE-C25 120 μm	DBE-821 240 μm	DBE-814 120 μm	DBE-224 120 μm
DBE-821 240 μm	DBE-311 120 μm	DBE-C25 240 μm	DBE-814 120 μm	PDMS 120 μm	DBE-224 240 μm	CMS-626 120 μm	Hemipasil X3 120 μm

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6

Table 1. Transmittance of each surface at a thickness of 120 μm and 240 μm before the immersion and after 8 months immersion in the *N. gaditana* culture.

Surface	Transmittance at 120 μm , %		Transmittance at 240 μm , %	
	Before immersion	After immersion	Before immersion	After immersion
DBE-814	36.2 \pm 2.5	35.8 \pm 3.9	13.8 \pm 1.0	10.7 \pm 3.1
DBE-224	79.3 \pm 5.2	54.0 \pm 5.9	65.9 \pm 4.1	32.4 \pm 3.6
Hempasil X3 [®]	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
OFX-0400	52.7 \pm 4.2	50.8 \pm 5.2	44.5 \pm 3.6	36.2 \pm 7.3
DBE-C25	49.5 \pm 2.6	51.5 \pm 8.9	37.6 \pm 2.1	35.1 \pm 5.9
DBE-311	97.7 \pm 3.3	98.4 \pm 3.6	93.7 \pm 4.1	95.1 \pm 3.8
DBE-821	44.6 \pm 2.0	22.3 \pm 2.7	24.4 \pm 1.0	15.3 \pm 3.9
PDMS	99.1 \pm 1.3	99.9 \pm 2.3	98.7 \pm 2.1	99.6 \pm 3.2
CMS-626	25.8 \pm 1.6	24.1 \pm 4.8	21.2 \pm 1.4	17.8 \pm 5.8
Borosilicate glass*		100.0 \pm 1.0		

*Commercial borosilicate glass (Normax[®], Portugal) has a thickness of 1 mm.

Table 2. Homogeneous group obtained for each factor (type of additive and immersion time) on fouling intensity and type of additive and thickness on microalga cell adhesion.

Variable	Factor	Value	Homogeneous group
Percentage of fouling intensity	Additive	DBE-311	X
		Hempasil X3®	X
		OFX-0400	X
		DBE-C25	X
		DBE-224	X
		DBE-814	X
		DBE-821	X
		PDMS	XX
		CMS-626	XX
		Glass	X
	Immersion time	0	X
		1	X
		3	X
6		X	
8		X	
Microalga cell adhesion	Additive	DBE-311	X
		Hempasil X3®	X
		OFX-0400	X
		DBE-C25	X
		DBE-224	X
		DBE-814	X
		DBE-821	X
		PDMS	X
		CMS-626	X
	Glass	X	
Thickness	120 µm	X	
	240 µm	X	

Table 3. Maximum photochemical photosystem II (Fv/Fm) yield and photosynthetic parameters (photosynthetic rate in the light-limited region (α), relative maximum electron transport rate ($rETR_{max}$) and the saturating irradiance (E_k)) at the initial state and at the end of the batch culture on each culture.

	Surface	Fv/Fm	Photosynthetic parameters		
			α , $\mu\text{mol e}^-$ $\mu\text{mol photons}^{-1}$	$rETR_{max}$, $\mu\text{mol e}^- \text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$	E_k , $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$
Initial state		0.637±0.008	0.26±0.07	17.72±3.61	67.00±6.69
End of batch culture	CMS-626	0.612±0.001	0.21±0.02	27.35±7.08	129.94±12.79
	Control	0.622±0.006	0.26±0.07	27.71±12.24	107.41±11.86
	DBE-224	0.612±0.001	0.23±0.06	27.85±8.52	121.30±10.29
	DBE-311	0.606±0.003	0.19±0.04	25.20±6.65	135.96±15.94
	DBE-814	0.618±0.004	0.24±0.04	28.03±10.41	116.61±10.72
	DBE-821	0.624±0.001	0.31±0.05	34.47±14.70	111.54±13.50
	DBE-C25	0.611±0.009	0.23±0.04	27.20±8.22	119.43±9.61
	OFX-0400	0.623±0.006	0.27±0.07	31.49±13.94	118.83±13.94
	PDMS	0.620±0.003	0.25±0.06	24.11±10.19	97.89±10.11
Glass	0.621±0.002	0.26±0.06	27.01±8.00	106.11±11.13	

Table S1. Value used in XDLVO theory for each variable.

Variable	Symbol	Value	Reference
Equivalent radius of the algal cell, m	a	$1.99 \cdot 10^{-6}$	Zeriouh et al., 2017b
Minimum separation distance between two surfaces, m	d_0	$1.57 \cdot 10^{-10}$	Boss et al., 1999
Electron charge, C	e	$1.60 \cdot 10^{-19}$	Zeriouh et al., 2017b
Ionic strength of the medium, mol m ⁻³	I	680.00	Zeriouh et al., 2017b
Boltzmann's constant, J K ⁻¹	k_B	$1.37 \cdot 10^{-23}$	Zeriouh et al., 2017b
Absolute temperature, K	T	298.00	
Dielectric constant of culture medium, F m ⁻¹	ϵ	$68.50 \cdot 10^{-10}$	Ellison et al., 1998
Zeta potential, V	ξ_m	$-6.60 \cdot 10^{-3}$	Zeriouh et al., 2017b
Inverse of double layer thickness, m ⁻¹	κ	$5.76 \cdot 10^8$	Calculated with equation 17
Correlation length, i.e., gyration radius of water molecules in a solution, m	λ	$6.00 \cdot 10^{-10}$	Zeriouh et al., 2017b
Hydration layer thickness associated with the algal cells, m	v	$3.00 \cdot 10^{-11}$	Ozkan et al., 2013b
Surface potential, V	ψ_s	$-6.92 \cdot 10^{-3}$	Zeriouh et al., 2017b
Cell surface potential, V	ψ_m	$-6.72 \cdot 10^{-3}$	Calculated with equation 16

1. Surface free energy calculation

The surface free energy (γ) is calculated from the measured contact angles (θ), as follows:

The interaction components of the surface free energy are calculated from Young's equation, using the experimental contact angle (θ) and bibliographic data for the solvent parameters (γ_i^{LW} , γ_i^- , γ_i^+ , γ_i). In the case of the present study those solvents are water, formamide and diiodomethane.

$$\cos(\theta) = -1 + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_{s,m}^{LW} \cdot \gamma_l^{LW})^{0.5}}{\gamma_l} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_{s,m}^+ \cdot \gamma_l^-)^{0.5}}{\gamma_l} + \frac{2 \cdot (\gamma_{s,m}^- \cdot \gamma_l^+)^{0.5}}{\gamma_l} \text{ (Young's equation)} \quad [1]$$

Bibliographic data (Bos et al. 1999)

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_D &= 50.8 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2}; \gamma_F = 58 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2}; \gamma_W = 72.8 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2}; \\ \gamma_D^{LW} &= 50.8 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2}; \gamma_F^{LW} = 39 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2}; \gamma_W^{LW} = 21.8 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2}; \\ \gamma_D^+ &= 0 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2}; \gamma_F^+ = 2.28 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2}; \gamma_W^+ = 25.5 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2}; \\ \gamma_D^- &= 0 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2}; \gamma_F^- = 39.6 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2}; \gamma_W^- = 25.5 \text{ mJ.m}^{-2} \end{aligned} \quad [2]$$

Young's equation is used with the value obtained for each solvent, so an equation system with 3 equations and 3 unknowns is solved. Then, the surface free energy interaction components are calculated (γ_s^{LW} , γ_s^+ , γ_s^- and/or γ_m^{LW} , γ_m^+ , γ_m^- , the subscript "s" refers to "substrate" as glass or coatings, and the subscript "m" refers to "microalga surface").

After that, the next surface free energy components could be calculated:

$$\gamma_s^{AB} = 2 \cdot \sqrt{\gamma_s^+ \cdot \gamma_s^-} \quad [3]$$

$$\gamma_m = \gamma_m^{AB} + \gamma_m^{LW} \quad [4]$$

And, finally, surface free energy is calculated as follow:

$$\gamma_s = \gamma_s^{AB} + \gamma_s^{LW} \quad [5]$$

Moreover, the degree of hydrophobicity of surfaces could be calculated with the cohesion free energy (ΔG_{coh}):

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_{coh-s.m} &= -2 \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_{s.m}^{LW}} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^{LW}} \right)^2 - [4(\sqrt{\gamma_{s.m}^+ \cdot \gamma_{s.m}^-} + \sqrt{\gamma_W^+ \cdot \gamma_W^-} \\ &\quad - \sqrt{\gamma_{s.m}^+ \cdot \gamma_W^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_{s.m}^- \cdot \gamma_W^+})] \end{aligned} \quad [6]$$

2. Thermodynamic approach

The interaction cell (m)-substrate (s) is calculated as follows:

$$\Delta G_{adh}^{LW} = -2 \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_m^{LW}} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^{LW}} \right) \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_s^{LW}} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^{LW}} \right) \quad [7]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_{adh}^{AB} = 2 \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_m^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_s^+} \right) \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_m^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_s^-} \right) - 2 \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_m^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^+} \right) \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_m^-} - \right. \\ \left. \sqrt{\gamma_W^-} \right) - 2 \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_s^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^+} \right) \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_s^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^-} \right) \end{aligned} \quad [8]$$

$$\Delta G_{adh} = \Delta G_{adh}^{AB} + \Delta G_{adh}^{LW} \quad [9]$$

And, in the case of two microalgae cells, the interaction cell (m₁)-cell (m₂):

$$\Delta G_{co-agg}^{LW} = -2 \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_{m1}^{LW}} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^{LW}} \right) \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_{m2}^{LW}} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^{LW}} \right) \quad [10]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_{co-agg}^{AB} = 2 \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_{m1}^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_{m2}^+} \right) \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_{m1}^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_{m2}^-} \right) - 2 \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_{m1}^+} - \right. \\ \left. \sqrt{\gamma_W^+} \right) \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_{m1}^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^-} \right) - 2 \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_{m2}^+} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^+} \right) \cdot \left(\sqrt{\gamma_{m2}^-} - \sqrt{\gamma_W^-} \right) \end{aligned} \quad [11]$$

$$\Delta G_{co-agg} = \Delta G_{co-agg}^{AB} + \Delta G_{co-agg}^{LW} \quad [12]$$

3. XDLVO theory

Once the surface is characterised, the XDLVO theory is applied as follows:

$$G^{LW}(d) = \frac{-A}{6} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{a}{d} + \frac{a}{d+2 \cdot a} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{d}{d+2 \cdot a} \right) \right] \quad [13]$$

$$A = -12 \cdot \pi \cdot d_0^2 \cdot \Delta G_{adh}^{LW} \quad [14]$$

$$G^{EL}(d) = \pi \cdot \varepsilon \cdot a \cdot (\psi_m^2 + \psi_s^2) \cdot \left[\frac{2 \cdot \psi_m \cdot \psi_s}{\psi_m^2 + \psi_s^2} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{1 + \exp(-\kappa \cdot d)}{1 - \exp(-\kappa \cdot d)} \right) + \ln(1 - \exp(-2 \cdot \kappa \cdot d)) \right] \quad [15]$$

$$\psi_m = \xi_m \cdot \left(1 + \frac{v}{a} \right) \cdot \exp(\kappa \cdot v) \quad [16]$$

$$\kappa = \left[\frac{e^2 \cdot I \cdot 6 \cdot 03 \cdot 10^{23}}{\varepsilon \cdot k_B \cdot T} \right]^{0.5} \text{ or } \kappa = \left[\frac{e^2}{\varepsilon \cdot k_B \cdot T} \cdot \sum z_i^2 \cdot n_i \right]^{0.5} \quad [17]$$

$$G^{AB}(d) = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot a \cdot \lambda \cdot \Delta G_{adh}^{AB} \cdot \exp \left(\frac{d_0 - d}{\lambda} \right) \quad [18]$$

Interaction cell (m₁)-cell (m₂)- configuration- two interacting spherical cells

$$G^{LW}(d) = \frac{-A \cdot a_2 \cdot a_1}{6 \cdot d \cdot (a_2 + a_1)} \quad [19]$$

$$A = -12 \cdot \pi \cdot d_0^2 \cdot \Delta G_{co-agg}^{LW} \quad [20]$$

$$G^{EL}(d) = \frac{\pi \cdot \varepsilon \cdot a_2 \cdot a_1 \cdot (\psi_{m1}^2 + \psi_{m2}^2)}{a_2 + a_1} \cdot \left[\frac{2 \cdot \psi_{m2} \cdot \psi_{m1}}{\psi_{m1}^2 + \psi_{m2}^2} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{1 + \exp(-\kappa \cdot d)}{1 - \exp(-\kappa \cdot d)} \right) + \ln(-2 \cdot \kappa \cdot d) \right] \quad [21]$$

$$G^{AB}(d) = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \frac{a_2 \cdot a_1}{a_2 + a_1} \cdot \lambda \cdot \Delta G_{co-agg}^{AB} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{d_0 - d}{\lambda}\right) \quad [22]$$

Finally, the total interaction energy is:

$$G^{TOT}(d) = G^{LW}(d) + G^{EL}(d) + G^{AB}(d) \quad [23]$$

Figure S1.

Figure captions

Figure S1. Biomass concentration (g L⁻¹) and Fv/Fm of each culture of the toxicity study. Circles correspond to biomass concentration of each culture and open triangular points correspond to the Fv/Fm.

Table S2. Adjusted p-value for each level difference at different time of immersion.

Level difference	Adjusted p-value			
	1 month	3 months	6 months	8 months
	immersion	immersion	immersion	immersion
CMS-626 – Glass	0.112	0.112	0.112	0.655
DBE-224 – Glass	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.448
DBE-311 – Glass	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
DBE-814 – Glass	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.368
DBE-821 – Glass	0.752	0.752	0.752	0.734
DBE-C25 – Glass	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
OFX-0400 – Glass	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
PDMS – Glass	0.788	0.788	0.788	0.977
Hempasil X3® - Glass	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000